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A potential early immune/senescence phenotype associated with BRCA1/2 mutation or loss.

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In this study we begin to distinguish or temporally separate BRCA2 defects, one of which appears to be an immune/senescence/presentation defect. The immune phenotype is likely dependent on a function for BRCA2 in DNA repair.

Determining if the immune phenotype is similar in transformed and non-transformed contexts will support understanding separate contributions of BRCA1/2 to transformation, a temporally complex process as immune changes may become evident at a time when transformation is still “occurring”, with contributions of BRCA1/2 to clearance of transformed cells after a tumor or group of cancer cells is present.

1 **Results**

2 GSE186733: healthy mammary epithelial cells from wild-type or BRCA2 mutant patients

3 In the breast, an altered NK signature is present prior to transformation.

4 CD160
5 CD84
6 CD80
7 CD244
8 CD247
9 CD248
10 NKG7

11 NKTR is modestly repressed in the apparently healthy BRCA2 mutant human breast epithelium.

12 HLA class I genes were affected by BRCA1/2 mutation status.

13 HLA-F, HLA-E, and HLA-J were each activated.

14 Chemokine expression was notably dysregulated in healthy non-transformed mammary epithelial cells from BRCA mutant patients.

15 GSE150067

16 BRCA2 iKO in HEK

17 In HEK293 cells, an altered senescence phenotype is present prior to/independence of transformation. Note that HEK293A are transformed. Nevertheless, an interferon signature/interferon activation is readily apparent, and these are not hematopoietic cells. The conclusion is that in a solid tissue, BRCA2 mutation or loss results in alterations in interferon activation that we are understanding to be a part of the senescence program, which has cell-intrinsic (cycle arrest) and cell-extrinsic implications (immune clearance via blood cell recruitment).

18 Interferon system was generally activated: this included:

19 IRF1 and IRF3;
20 IRF7, IRF5 and IRF4
21 IRF2BPL
22 IFITM2 and IFITM3
23 IFI35 and IFI27
24 IFIT3 and IFIT2
25 IFIH1 (MDA5)
26 IFRD1

27 NCR3LG1 and NKTR are activated upon BRCA2 loss in HEK293.

1 Changes in any of the following are not measured/recorded (this is a heterologous system), unlike what
2 we observed in the non-transformed, healthy human breast:

3 CD160
4 CD84
5 CD80
6 CD247
7 CD248
8 NKG7

9 TIPARP (PARP7) is activated; PARP7 is a repressor/regulator of AHR, which we are currently finding to be
10 involved in or expressed in the context of senescence processes in non-hematopoietic tissues (re: BRCA2
11 immune phenotype).

12 Class I was again activated: HLA-B, HLA-C and HLA-E.

13 The following cluster of differentiation molecules were dysregulated by BRCA2 ko in HEK293:

14 CD44 is activated (stem/progenitor)
15 CD68 is activated (phagocytosis/debris)
16 CD99 is silenced
17 CD163L1 is activated (anti-inflammatory macrophage, IL-10 associated)
18 CD320 is repressed (expressed in Tfh and NK CD56 bright)
19 CD109 is activated (not an NK marker but associated with Tgd activation [gdT])
20 CD9 is repressed (distinguishes decidual NK cells from other NK types)
21 CD59 is activated (complement associated - MAC)
22 CD70 is activated (expressed on activated T and B, and following NK cell IL-15 activation; TNF
23 superfamily associated)
24 CD24 is activated (stem/progenitor)

25 GSE165914: BRCA deficiency in a transformed context; with and without PARP inhibition.

26 Programmed cell death genes PDCD2, 4, 5, 11 were silenced or repressed in HEK upon BRCA2 loss.
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Methods

We used systems biologic methodologies to understanding how germline mutation in BRCA DNA repair genes affect cell and molecular biology in an unbiased manner.

We also consulted other whole transcriptome datasets that facilitate study of BRCA1 or BRCA2 mutation.

- GSE239857
- GSE234017
- GSE211729
- GSE185314